

Challenging Assumptions about Women's Empowerment and Economic Resources and Domestic Violence among Young Married Women in India

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Abstract

The research has documented the extensive prevalence of spousal violence in India little is known about specific risk or protective factors. This study examines the relationships that are often observed to be social and economic resources for women and the occurrence of domestic violence. Over half (56%) of the study participants reported having ever experienced physical spousal violence; about a quarter (27%) reported violence. Based on our study and research, it is clear that India has to do some structural reforms and efforts to help women empower themselves through vocational training, employment opportunities, and social groups.

Keywords: economic and social resources, gender, women's empowerment

JEL Codes: I10, I20

1. Introduction

Over a decade ago, the United Nations General Assembly called for increased research into the 'causes, nature, sincerity and consequences of violence against women, following a detection that such violence represents a fundamental violation of women's health and human rights. Since then, studies across India have documented the widespread prevalence of domestic violence, encircling an array of physical, sexual, and/or psychological acts delivered by intimate male partners. For example, several South Asian studies have examined the role of inconvenience, such as lower household socioeconomic status, level of education, low earning potential, and young age at marriage and have found these factors to be linked with higher reported physical violence. On the other hand, other studies have found no relationship between household poverty and violence or a positive relationship between women's level of education and violence. The links between gender-based power and domestic violence are widely considered, with violence being viewed both as a demonstration of deeply entrenched gender power inequities as well as a mechanism by which such inequities are imposed. For instance, studies in South Asia have examined women's power in marital relationships in terms of power arising from conformed to social medium and expectations, such as how big a dowry she has brought to the marital household. Women with relatively smaller dowries, those whose in-laws have expressed frustration with their dowries, and those who have faced post-marriage dowry requests have been repeatedly found to be more likely to report domestic violence. Research in Tamil Nadu indicates that items given as dowry may provide a woman with financial resources that allow her to contract her status in the marital household. Studies have provided inconsistent information on the association between violence and women's empowerment, particularly in terms of economic opportunity, control of assets, and social group participation. While women with greater economic resources, such as ownership of land, jewelry, and other valuables, were less likely to report violence in one study, employed women have been found to report violence more frequently than unemployed women in several other studies. The health implications for women who participate in community social groups have not been examined in India. The Samata Health Project is a successful women's health research study looking at issues of gender, sexuality, reproductive health, violence, and sexually transmitted infection (STI) and HIV prevention among unsaved women and men in Bangalore, the capital city of Karnataka state in southern India.

2. Literature Review

Jejeebhoy and Cook (1997) investigated the impact of state accountability for wife beating, the Indian challenge. India was restricted under International law to reduce violence against women including wife beating. Indian Government along with 186 other UN member states adopted the platform held in Beijing in 1995 for the deduction of this violence. The conclusion of the community study was to the adoption of strategies to attack violence is needed urgently to address the needs of women suffering from violence in short term and solve the main causes of violence in long term and bring about the social, economic, and legal equality of genders directed by the Indian Constitution. Jeyaseelan et al., (2007) analyzed the physical spousal violence against women in India; some risk factors. In developing counties like India, domestic women violence had become a general problem holding back development. In the rural, urban, and urban-slum areas across seven cities in India, a survey was taken out among the women between the ages of 15-49 years, living with a child less than 18 years of age. The probability proportionate to size method was used. The outcome indicated three physical violence behaviors of hit, kick and beat. Of 9938 women surveyed 26% reported complaining about physical violence against them during the period of their marriage. The adjusted odds ratios calculated suggested that women whose husbands consume alcohol on daily bases (OR 5.6; 95% CI 4.7-6.6) who experienced dowry harassment (OR 3.2; 95%

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C2.7-3.8) who experienced harsh childhood punishment (OR 1.6; 95% CI 1.4-1.8) were at increased risk of spousal physical violence.

Koenig et al., (2006) examined the individual and community level influences on domestic violence in north India (Uttar Pradesh). To explore domestic violence outcomes among a sample of 4520 married men the multilevel modeling method was used. Physical and sexual domestic violence was linked with the individual level variables of childlessness, economic pressure, and intergenerational transmission of violence. A community of violent crime was connected with the elevated risks of both physical and sexual violence. Community level standards concerning wife beating were significantly associated only with physical violence. In risk factors for physical and sexual domestic violence, important similarities and dissimilarities were noticeable. To be protected against physical violence higher socioeconomic status was found. Shaping the women's risks of sexual and physical violence the results provide additional support for the importance of contextual factors. Ackerson et al., (2008) examined the role of women's education and proximate educational context on intimate partner violence (IPV). According to the Indian National Family Health Survey a sample of 83627 married women aged 15 to 49 years from 1998 to 1999. Multilevel multiple logistic regression modeling methods are used to estimate the effect of women's and their husband's level of education, spousal education differential, and community-level literacy on women's risk of recent and lifetime IPV. Among women without education odds of IPV were 5.61 times (95% CI=3.53, 8.92) those of college-educated women, odds among wives of uneducated men were 1.84 times (95% CI=1.44, 2.35) those of wives of college-educated men. For the reduction of IPV for women increasing women's level of education is important. Schuler et al., (1996) examined credit programs, Patriarchy, and men's violence against women in rural Bangladesh. In Bangladesh, violence by men against women occurred within the house in most cases. But it was neither generating in-house nor limited within the house. It makes women dependent on the social standard that defines women's place. Ethnographic and structured survey data are used in this paper. The outcomes of the study suggest that men's violence against women can be reduced through group-based credit programs that can make women's lives more social. The problem of men's violence is deeply rooted and the authors argue that to diminish this violence much more extensive measures will be required.

Srinivasan and Bedi (2007) investigated domestic violence and dowry: evidence from a South Indian village. The dowry system has observed sharp changes in South India in recent years. The average payments of dowry have risen and become a phenomenon for all classes. The changes bring several negative results for women including their survival. Despite these outcomes, the practice of dowry continues without any reduction. Based on a micro-level study this paper examines the link between dowry and domestic violence. The study showed that dowry has a negative relation to inter-spousal violence. Marital violence can be reduced by increasing the economic resources of the marital household. Which enhances the social status of the groom and his family. Women's education tends to be linked with an increase in the level of violence. Heise and Garcia-Moreno (2002) analyzed the link between the multidimensional aspects of gender inequity and the risk of intimate partner violence IPV. The demographic health survey method is used and the data for the year 2007 was taken from Bangladesh. The analysis was based on the response of 4,467 married women. The main describing variable is Gender Inequality. According to the results, physical and sexual violence was experienced by 53% of married women. Women who had a higher level of independence (adjusted odds ratio "AOR" 0.48; 99% CI 0.37-0.61), a high level of economic decision-making independence (AOR 0.12; 99% CI 0.08-0.17), and a higher level of non-supportive attitudes towards wife beating or raping (AOR 0.61; 99% CI 0.47-0.83) were less likely to report having experienced IPV. Age at marriage, education level, and professional disagreement between partners were also found to be remarkable predictors of IPV. Rao (1997) inspect wife-beating in rural South India. Ethnographic and econometric methods were used in this paper to examine the motives of wife abuse in Southern India. The qualitative analysis exhibit that wife abuse is more likely when dowries are witnessed as lacking/not enough when the causes of the abuse are recognized as acceptable by the community and when husbands are alcoholic. The hypothesis achieved from the qualitative analysis was tested with survey data which clearly shows that smaller dowry payments and consumption of alcohol were the main causes that the risk of wife beating naturally increased. Furthermore, the statistical analysis reveals that women are more likely to be abused who are disinfectured or have more female children.

Malhotra (1991) explores gender and changing generational relations. The state of being married development was experienced by many Asian societies that are not only fixed as fundamental to other conditions of the family organization but is more difficult than standard study of female age at marriage can tell. Parental control of marriage is examined to see how it has changed over time and which factors are involved to affect the spouse selection process. To see whether men and women are similarly forced in the choice of a partner or whether there is a fundamental gender, inequality in these constraints, and the factors impacting them we focus on gender differences. There is an increasing identification in the literature that a focus on intergenerational relations is important to understanding the family structure and its relation to demographic structure behavior. Koenig et al., (2003) explore women's status and domestic violence in two rural areas of Bangladesh and found increased education, higher socioeconomic status, extended family residence, and non-Muslim religion to be linked with

lower risks of violence. In the more culturally conservative areas, higher women's independence and short-term membership in savings and credit groups were both linked with significantly high risks of violence, and community-level variables were associated with violence. In the less culturally conservative area, in contrast, women, status indicators were unlinked to the risk of violence, and community-level measures of women's status were linked with significantly lower risks of violence, apparently by increasing imperfect regulative changes in gender relations. Nathan (2004) investigated the trauma of wage employment and the burden of work for women in India. From 2005-2006, 744 married women aged 16-25, who live in low-income communities in Bangalore, India were enrolled in the study. At enrollment data were collected, at 12 and 24 months. Multivariable logistic regression models are used to examine the association between women's status of employment, their awareness of their husband's employment stability, and domestic violence. Women who were unemployed at one visit and began employment by the next visit had an 80% higher odds of violence, as compared to women who maintained their unemployed status. Similarly, women whose husbands had stable employment at one visit and newly had difficulty with employment had 1.7 times the odds of violence as compared to women whose husbands maintained their stable employment.

Kabeer (1999) investigated resources agency achievements and reflections of women's empowerment. The paper was to understand women's empowerment so that women can obtain the ability to make well-thought-out choices for their lives who have been rejected to obtain such ability. The ability to utilize choice includes three correlated measurements: resources (future claims to material, human and social resources), agency (the process of decision making, deception, and manipulation), and achievements (well-being outcomes). The paper argues that in determining the meaning of an indicator these three dimensions of choice are invisible. The opinion of choice is further qualified by referring to the conditions of choice its content and consequence. These qualifications represent an attempt to incorporate the structural parameters of individual choice in the analysis of women's empowerment. Krishnan (2005) examined do structural inequalities contribute to marital violence. To explore the context in which marital violence occurs and the relationships between structural inequalities (gender, caste, and class inequalities) and marital violence Ethnographic research was conducted in rural communities in Karnataka state, South India. The research highlighted that a) marital violence is well linked to the experience of gender, caste, and class inequalities b) women's ability to prevent violence link to access to economic and social resources and c) To be actively involved in responding to violence health care providers need. The study shows the urgent need for violence prevention resources, particularly those that address the contribution of structural inequalities. Vyas and Kumaranayake (2006) examined Constructing socio-economic status indices: how to use principal components analysis. For health research and policy, inventions were concerned that there was a differential impact concerning health outcomes or health services utilization based on socio-economic status (SES). The information about how households vary by SES is central to the question that how to target the poorest. Standard economic measures of SES use monetary information such as income data is a demanding task. By comparison, consumption or expenditure measures are much more reliable and easier to collect than income. Interpretation of results and methods of classifying households into SES groups are also discussed. PCA has been validated as a method to describe SES.

Ruiz-Perez et al., (2007) analyzed methodological issues in the study of violence against women. The objective of the paper is to review the methodological issues that arise when studying violence against women as a public health problem focusing on intimate partner violence (IPV), This type of violence that has the greatest consequences at a social and political level. The paper focuses first on the problems of defining what is meant by IPV. Secondly, the paper describes the difficulties in assessing the magnitude of the problem. Because of the methodological issues obtaining reliable data is a complex task. The methodological problem related to the type of sampling used in both aetiological and prevalence studies. India International Institute of Population Science (2005-2006) examined the national family health survey-3. The NFHS is a largescale multi-round scale conducted on a representative sample of households throughout India. Technical assistance for the NFHS was provided by ORC macro and East-West Centre. The third FHS (NFHS-3) was carried out in 2005-2006. Eighteen research organizations including five population research Centres surveyed in 29 states of India. The funding for NFHS-3 is provided by USAID, DFID, The Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, UNICEF, UNFPA and MOHFW, GOI. ORC Macro and USA is providing technical assistance for NFHS-3 and NARI are providing technical assistance for HIV component. Bloch and Rao (2002) investigated terror as a bargaining instrument: a case study of dowry violence. In contrast to most dowry-oriented societies in which payments have declined with modernization, those in India have experienced suggestive extension over the last five decades. The paper explains the difference between these two experiences by focusing on the role played by caste. The theoretical model compares caste and non-caste-based societies. There exists a rooted component to status (caste) that is independent of wealth. Modernization is assumed to involve the following components: increasing average wealth and increasing health distribution within status (or caste) groups. The paper shows that in caste-based societies the increase in health distribution leads to an increase in dowry payments. Whereas in non-caste-based societies increased dispersion has no real effects on dowry payments and an increase in average wealth causes a decline in payments.

Mody (2002) examined love and law as love and marriage in Delhi. In 1860 the colonial state received an application constituted for marriages among their members so that they could freely marry according to their rights of conscience. The governor general council began to consider the introduction of civil marriage law for all Indians. The law of civil marriage was nonetheless passed by which two Indians could constitute marry out of choice and love. These debates illustrate the legitimacy of marriage conceived as an individual contract as opposed to a social one that admits no agency on the part of the couple and concentrates agency entirely within a community. In North India marriage amongst Hindus is seen as a religious union. Amongst Muslims, it is viewed as a contract. In the words of a Brahman: Love is a gift from God gifted to two people on the day of their marriage "Love isn't something that one does that is lust. Love is given only by God." Srinivasan (2005) examined Daughter or Dowries. The changing nature of dowry practices in South India. Significant changes have occurred in the practice of dowry in South India. From being an upper caste practice, dowry has become an all-class phenomenon, replacing the symbolic exchange of gifts between the families of the groom and bride. Tamil Nadu ranks third among 15 major Indian states on the human development index. A particularly disturbing trend recently reported is the worsening of the 0-6 sex ratio. Dowry is reported as the number one cause of the unwontedness of daughters. At present most boys and girls attend the primary school located in the village. The minimum level of education has risen over the years for all castes. Dowry is primarily transferred from the woman's natal family to the woman, her husband, and his family at the time of marriage. In conclusion, there is a need to address the problem of dowry as much as wider. Corinne et al., (2008) examined the paper declaration on the elimination of violence against women and examines the knowledge, attitude, and actions of health professionals towards women experiencing spousal violence. A descriptive survey of 134 randomly selected respondents out of 572 health professionals in a tertiary health institution in South Western. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics. 38% of cases of violence against women (VAW) may not be identified and 42% of the identified cases would not be properly managed. (143) health workers participated. (56.7%) were nurses and (43.3%) were medical doctors. The age range of the respondents was 20-58 years.

Verma (2003) examined wife beating and the link between poor sexual health and risk behavior among men in urban slums in India to understand the nature of men's extramarital in three low-income communities in Mumbai, India. Explore the associations between marital relationships and extramarital sex and assess the implications of the research results for intervention. Results are based on survey data collected from 2,408 randomly selected men. These Surveys produced a unique data set that allows sociodemographic, attitudinal, and behavioral variables from husband and wife. The predominance of marriages in communities (Muslims, Hindus) are arranged which means that most wives and husbands come together as virtual strangers. At the time of the survey, 16% of married men were living without their wives. Ghimire et al., (2006) examined the consequences of nonfamily experiences on participation in the selection of a first companion in an arranged marriage society. The authors developed a theoretical structure to explain how a vast pattern of nonfamily experiences may translate into greater participation in the choice of a partner. The investigation shows that premarital nonfamily experience in general and media exposition and presence in youth clubs, in particular, have strong positive effects on individual participation in the choice of a partner. These findings suggest a new wage of thinking about the relationship between social change and the shift away from an arranged marriage. Overall, changes in these nonfamily experiences can report an extraordinary division of the historical increase of youth involvement in mate selection.

3. The Model

In this study, we include four variables. Education is used as the dependent variable to measure the effect of women's empowerment while age dependency and school enrollment are used as concerned variables or foremost variables. While the population is used as the control variable. In our model, the effect of women's empowerment is measured by education while school enrollment and age dependency are concerned variables. On the other hand, the population is taken as the control variable. So, we will find the impact of women empowerment on the education of India by using both indicators such as age and school enrollment. Following the previous literature (Ali and Naeem, 2017; Ali, 2011; Ali, 2015; Ali, 2018; Ali and Bibi, 2017; Ali and Ahmad, 2014; Ali and Audi, 2016; Ali and Audi, 2018; Ali and Rehman, 2015; Ali and Senturk, 2019; Ali and Zulfiqar, 2018; Ali et al., 2016; Ali et al., 2021; Ali et al., 2021; Ali et al., 2015; Arshad and Ali, 2016; Ashraf and Ali, 2018; Audi et al., 2022; Audi and Ali, 2017; Audi and Ali, 2017; Audi et al., 2021; Audi and Ali, 2016; Audi et al., 2021; Audi et al., 2021; Audi et al., 2021; Haider and Ali, 2015; Kaseem et al., 2019; Roussel et al., 2021; Sajid and Ali, 2018; Senturk and Ali, 2021; Mehmood et al., 2022; Ali et al., 2022; Ahmad et al., 2022; Sulehri and Ali, 2020; Ali et al., 2021; Alim et al., 2022), the model will become as:

$$\text{Edu} = f(\text{S.E, AGE, POP})$$

By applying the log on each side of the equation, the estimation form of our model becomes

$$\text{Ln Edu} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LnS.E} + \beta_2 \text{LnAGE} + \beta_3 \text{LnPOP} + \varepsilon$$

Where

$$\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3 > 0$$

Where $\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2,$ and β_3 are used as parameters of independent variables or slope of the model.

Edu= Education (% female)

S. E= School enrollment

AGE= Age dependency

POP= Population

ξ = error Term

For the estimation, the data has been taken for 36 years for the period of (1980-2016). The source of data is World Development Indicators (WDI). In this study to find the long-run and short-run relationships among the variables, we will apply the co-integration testing with the use of Granger causality or co-integration models like the ARDL (Autoregressive distributive lag) model or Johansson co-integration.

Table 1: Variable Measurement

Variable	Measurement
Dependent Variable	
Education	Primary education pupils as (percentage of female)
Independent Variables	
1. School Enrollment	School enrollment primary female (% gross)
2. Age Dependency	Age Dependency ratio, young (% of working age pop)
3. Population	Population ages 15-64, female (% of total)

4. Data and Methodology

In this study, data has been comprised of 36 years from 1980 to 2016. To analyze this study the data has been extracted from the World Development Indicators (WDI). After the data has been collected we have to estimate the co-integration of variables to find the long-run and short-run relationship among the variables. After that, we have to check the stationarity to apply a specific model/ applying the model is necessary to find the appropriate estimates of the variables. The main source by which we can find the stationarity and non-stationarity is the unit root test. We can define it as in the absence of unit root the data in time series is stationary. While on the other hand if the unit root test is present we can say that the data in the time series is non-stationary. This shows that the unit root test is the main source to find the stationarity and non-stationarity. We know that the main objective of co-integration is to find the long-run relationship which we then employ in Error Correction Model. By considering the other models like Engle-Granger in 1987, the co-integration process is not possible if the integration of the variables is defined as (for variable M i.e. $I(1)$ and for variable N, i.e. $I(0)$). On the other hand, Johnson in 1980, Auto-Regressive distributive Lag model (ARDL), the co-integration process is possible if the integration of the variables is different. In our study after applying the Augmented Dicky Fuller Test we find that three of four variables (EDU, Age dependency, and population) are stationary at level i.e. $I(0)$ and the remaining variable (School enrollment) is stationary at first difference i.e. $I(1)$. According to the conditions of the co-integration model ARDL model is applicable in this case. A simple term for the ARDL model which is specifically termed "Bewley transformation" which allows estimating the long-run coefficients gives the advantage of the Engle-Granger causality approach. It is preferable to use the ARDL when the different variables are integrated differently like $I(0)$ and $I(1)$. Among the small sample of variables, there is a long-run relationship through the Wald test mostly known as F-statistics. And here we can say that in ARDL long-run relationship establishment approach exists when F-statistics approach critical value. In ARDL co-integration the unit root test for the second difference is not applicable. The main condition is the presence of $I(0)$ and $I(1)$ at the same time otherwise it would be considered wrongly interpreted or a misunderstanding of the ARDL technique. Theoretically, it is explained by the economists that there exists a long-run relationship among the variables used in the ARDL model.

The advantage of the ARDL model is that it uses a single equation with one dependent variable and the other is taken as independent or exogenous variables. In the ARDL model, there are many co-integrated variables. The major advantage of this model is that it makes the specification of these variables very easy. Another advantage of the ARDL model is that the ECM model can also be integrated from this model to find the long-run and short-run relationships without losing the information on long-run integration information. To apply the ARDL model first all unit root test is applied to check the stationarity as $I(0)$ and $I(1)$. After finding the long-run relationship among the integrated variables by using the F-statistics we will find the maximum lag length by using the lag length criteria. This is the standard way to find the optimal lag length. There are so many criteria by which we can select an appropriate lag for our model such as Akaike information criterion (AIC), Hannan-Quinn information criterion (HQ), Schwarz information criterion (SC), etc. But we will select the appropriate Lag for our model through the Akaike information criterion (AIC). After finding the lag length we will apply the bound test to check the long-run relationship by accepting or rejecting the hypothesis. After the long-run relationship, the next step is now to find the long-run coefficients by applying the Auto Regressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) approach to cointegration. After this step, we will find the causality by applying the causality test. Finally, to find the short-run and long-run coefficients we will apply the Cusum test.

5. Results of Estimation

In the first step of our analysis, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test is used for testing the stationary level of all the time series Edu, age, and population variables are stationary at level I(0). While S.E enrollment is non-stationary at the level. When we take their first differences they become stationary I (1). As shown in Table 1. The results of the unit root test suggested that the ARDL model is applicable here because the variables either at level or first difference are stationary and non-stationary. This model is also applicable because none of the variables is stationary at the second level or second difference. After suggesting the appropriate model, we will apply the lag length criteria to check the optimal lag length. There are different criteria to check the optimality but we will check the lag length by using the Akaike Information Criteria (AIC). According to Akaike Information Criteria lag, 3 is appropriate to check the optimal lag length. After applying the lag length, we will apply the bound test to check the long-run relationship. The bound test identifies whether the variables in the model have a long-run relationship or not.

H_0 : There is no long-run relationship between variables

H_1 : There is a long-run relationship between the variables

The criteria are rejecting H_0 if the F-statistic is greater than the upper bound limit of any given significant level.

$$10.78 > 4.35 \text{ (At the level of 5\%)}$$

So, we can reject our null hypothesis means we are accepting our alternative hypothesis that there exists a long-run relationship between education (edu), population (pop), school enrollment(se), and age dependency (age). After the long-run relationship, the next step is now to find the long-run coefficients by applying the Auto Regressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) approach to co-integration. As shown in Table 5. Women empowerment has a negative relationship with education as shown by the negative sign in the long run. the negative sign indicates that if education is increased in the country it will decrease women's empowerment in the country in the long run. The criteria for Rejecting the null hypothesis is that if the Probability value is significant then reject the null hypothesis.

Table 2

Null Hypothesis	F-Statistic	Prob.	Results
POP does not Granger Cause LA	0.41989	0.7402	Do not reject the null hypothesis
LA does not Granger Cause POP	10.78	0.133	Reject null hypothesis

Finally, CUSUM TEST is used to check the stability of the data. our results show that our data is stable. The results are shown in Table 10.

Table 3

Variables	Order	Critical Value (1%)	Critical Value (5%)	Critical Value (10%)	Test Statistics	Prob
EDU	Level	-3.632900	-2.948404	-2.612874	-2.818148	0.0660
School Enrollment	Level	-3.632900	-2.948404	-2.612874	-2.608289	0.1009
	1st Difference	-3.639407	-2.951125	-2.614300	-4.548345	0.0009
Age	Level	-4.243644	-3.544284	-3.204699	-3.371424	0.0718
Pop	Level	-3.632900	-2.948404	-2.612874	-6.079554	0.000

In this study, the above table shows the results of the unit root test. According to this table, School enrollment is stationary at first difference. While pop and ages are stationary at level. There is no long-run relationship among the variables. This table shows a negative relationship between education and women empowerment. It means that if education increases then women's empowerment will decrease. As India is a country that has great benefits in women empowerment concerning education. But during previous years this sector has been greatly affected due to various reasons like increased risk of domestic violence. Women empowerment can be improved by vocational training, employment opportunities, and social groups.

Table 4: Lag Length Criteria

HQ	Lags	Akaike Information Criteria (AIC)
0	3.673915	3.643296
1	14.88598	14.79412
2	18.24993	18.09684
3	19.01421*	18.79988*

By using this lag criterion, we have concluded that Lag 3 is the optimal Lag length.

Bond Test Results: Table 5

T-Stats	Value	K
F-Stats	4.3003	
Critical Value Bounds		
Significance	I0 Bound	I1 Bound
10%	2.72	3.77
5%	3.23	4.35
2.5%	3.69	4.89
1%	4.29	5.61

The above-bound test results show that $10.78 > 4.01$ (At a level of 5%)
 So, we can reject our null hypothesis means we are accepting our alternative hypothesis that there exists a long-run relationship between education (edu), population (pop), age dependency (age), and school enrollment (se).

Table 6
 ARDL estimates, (1,0,0,0), EDU is Taken as dependent variable

Regressors	Coefficient	Std.Error	T-statistics	Prob
EDU(-1)	0.495038	0.175661	2.818148	0.0082
POP (-1)	-1.061657	0.010142	-6.079554	0.000
SE (-1)	-1.279383	0.281285	-4.548345	0.0001
LA	-0.031292	0.011714	-2.671400	0.011
R-Squared	0.2502	F-Stats	8.402199	
S.E of Regression	1.45326	Durbin-Watson Stat	1.998288	

Estimated Long Run Measurement: Table 7

Regressors	Coefficients	Std.Error	T-Statistics	Prob
POP	0.158851	0.081681	1.944761	0.0606
SE	0.079705	0.061252	1.301250	0.2025
AGE	0.016882	0.041435	0.407437	0.6864

The above table shows that Education has a positive relationship with pop. It means that a 1 unit change in Edu pop will change by 0.15%.

Estimated Short Run Measurements Table 8

Variable	Coefficients	Std.Error	T-Stats	Prob
Edu	0.338152	0.080834	4.183308	0.0002
<u>POP</u>	0.056437	0.050531	1.116869	0.2724
<u>SE</u>	0.011954	0.029454	0.405844	0.6876
<u>AGE</u>	-0.008362	0.032233	-0.259425	0.7970

Our table shows that Education is positively and significantly related to pop. It means that a one percent change in Edu will also change the pop by 1%.

Table 9: Diagnostic Result for Granger Causality

Problems	F-Test	Probabilities
Serial correlation	0.2830	0.7789
Heteroscedasticity	0.2377	0.91

The assumption of ARDL explains that the results must be free from Autocorrelation. H_0 =There is no autocorrelation. Here the p-value shows that $0.7789 > 0.05$ so we cannot reject the H_0 .so our model is free from serial correlation similarly the P value $0.91 > 0.05$ which shows that the model is also free from heteroskedasticity.

The above graph shows that data of this study is stable. The blue line in the Graph shows the Stability of the data. There is no heteroscedasticity and no Autocorrelation in the data.

6. Conclusion and Policy Implications

In our Research, we have studied the women empowerment's impacts on the education of India. According to this research, education can be effective for women's empowerment by investing in vocational training institutes and job opportunities. The study findings suggest that the effectiveness of anti-dowry laws may be limited without additional strategies that prepare women, families, and communities to challenge the widespread acceptance of dowry and promote gender equity. Extensive studies are needed to demonstrate the complex causal relationships

between 'love' marriages and domestic violence. The government should do reforms for the education of women. The government should invest in vocational institutions to make women more empowered. India should also make structural changes like providing more job opportunities.

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